

ISic1080

I.Sicily inscription 1080

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Phintias

Place of origin (modern)

Licata

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Licata

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140562

1. [—]ΩN[—]NYM [— —]

2. [—]ΦΩN [— — — —]

3. [— — —]KPATH [—]

4. [— — —]PETΩ [— —]

5. [— — —]ΩN [— — —]

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492708

EDCS 39102237

PHI 140562

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0260 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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